

Chengdu's Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, 2022 cohort

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student-generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws on prior research and engagement projects to visualise entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which teams of students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals to advance the ecosystem.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

General Methodology

In partnership with Investment NSW (e.g., Sydney Startup Hub) and Spark Festival, the cohort of ~45 students was given the option to focus on Sydney CBD, Western Sydney, or Nationally. Additionally, one team was based overseas and was free to choose an international city to navigate.

The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,³ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE).

In addition to learning about ecosystems, teams engaged with ecosystems in authentic and immersive learning experiences. Stakeholder types and specific stakeholders in the ecosystem were identified based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. Insights about the ecosystem were generated by analysing desktop reports and media interviews involved those stakeholders. Where possible, teams conducted their own interviews of key stakeholders, including asking them about the ecosystem's history, evolution and critical events, and their vision for how it may evolve further. By synthesising such reports and interviews from multiple stakeholders, teams developed a composite story of the ecosystem's evolution, visualised its current state and identified specific opportunities for change. These reports present this analysis of the ecosystems' evolution as well as the team's proposal for specific interventions by which to intentionally advance the ecosystem in a specific direction.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

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1 Evolution of the Ecosystem

Chengdu Hi-tech Development Zone, referred to as CDHT, consists of five areas: Hi-tech West Zone, South Zone, East Zone, Bio Town and Finance and business District. We think the most effective way to tell the history of this vibrant ecosystem is through a linear timeline.

Looking at the development of CDHT from a regional perspective, CDHT has grown from a single area of 24.6 square kilometres planned in 1988 to a total area of 234 square kilometers now, providing a broad space for industrial gathering scientific and technological innovation and entrepreneurial development.

Looking at the development of CDHT from the perspective of industry, CDHT has developed from a single electronic information industry at the beginning to a 3+2 industrial form of electronic information, bio-medical, new economy and modern service and future industry, which constitute the industrial support for the high-quality development of Chengdu High-tech Zone (Op-ed by Guilherme Campos, 2021).

In 1988, an important milestone in the first decade of China's reform and opening up, the "Torch Plan" (Appendix) was formally implemented. As the forerunner of the historical change, Chengdu Municipal Party Committee has a keen awareness of the changes of The Times. In the same year, the Municipal Party committee submitted the work report of the development zone. The "Torch Project" was officially implemented. Two of the goals are to "build and develop high-tech Industrial Development Zone" and "establish the Embassy of the People's Republic of China in Ireland" (n.d.). It can be said that Cdht has been an incubator since the beginning of its development.

In 1990, Chengdu High-tech Entrepreneurship Service Center, the largest incubator building in China at that time, was officially completed, which marked the beginning of CDHT's business incubation. After entering the 21st century. With the establishment of the incubation park, the birth of in-depth incubators divided by industry, such as the Software Pioneer Park, and the establishment of the "innovation park" at Sichuan University (SCU) and the University of Electronic Science and Technology of China (UESTC), the innovation in the three industrial fields of CDHT began to accelerate. It provides more comprehensive services and support for entrepreneurs and start-ups, greatly improving the local entrepreneurship and innovation environment. Because of this, the talents and projects generated by these incubators remain in the region, thus promoting steady economic growth. The development of CDHT helps to break through geographical constraints and connect researchers and emerging talents in various fields across the country and the world. The integration of industry, education, and research.

The innovation industry of CDHT is growing every year. With the precipitation of time, policy support and the construction of stakeholders, the entrepreneurial ecosystem of CDHT has become mature and entered a positive cycle, followed by international cooperation and professional construction. The Centre for China-Europe Cooperation (CCEC) began construction in 2013 and was put into use in 2017(EU SME Centre, 2017). The project aims to promote all-around cooperation between Chinese and European enterprises in capital, brand management, market expansion, technology transfer and transaction, as well as project development and opening, bringing more international perspectives to existing enterprises and start-ups. In 2017, CDHT released the construction scheme of high-tech service supermarket, can foresee the move to make consolidation of new and high technology, breakthrough time and space constraints, obtain technology services at domestic and overseas(Xue, 2017), according to the plan, will also extend "innovation chain, the chain of assets, capital chain" realize the gathering of all kinds of factors of innovation and transformation, all-round services to improve the enterprise incubator. The CDHT region is gradually perfecting its innovation-oriented ecosystem.

Figure 1: Evolution of the Chengdu High-Tech Zone

2 Ecosystem Mapping

The ecosystem map (Figure 2) can clearly show the relationship between the various stakeholders that constitute the ecosystem, and can help investors and government managers to familiarize themselves with the interaction mechanism and components among various stakeholders, improve leadership operator's work efficiency. When interpreting the ecosystem map, it should be noted that the stakeholders in the ecosystem are visualized according to their relationship to the ecosystem.

Policy

Policies play an important role in the construction of ecosystems. Leadership and policies promulgated by local governments will affect the development zone to attract enterprises and multi-party institutions (such as educational institutions, research institutes, financial institutions, etc.) to join. Local government policies and leadership are committed to encouraging different industries to join the development zone, providing funding or talent assistance for institutional investment and entry.

Supports

Infrastructure and non-government institutions are important elements of the ecosystem, which attract talents and people around the ecosystem for the construction of the ecosystem, improve the passenger flow of the ecosystem, and medical institutions provide services for entrepreneurial activities in the region and improve the efficiency and safety of ecological activities.

Finance

Financial institutions are a key element in promoting the sustainable development of the ecosystem. As important local banking institutions, the major banks and lending institutions in the development zone have driven the economic development of the development zone and are an important source of funds for the development of the ecosystem.

Culture

Cultural service centres such as the Chengdu Medical Association and the library provide key medical services and knowledge services for the construction of the ecosystem and build a network and bridge of knowledge services for the construction of the ecosystem.

Market

The participation of financial exchange and import and export enterprises has attracted external investment, broadened the development network of the ecosystem, attracted the investment and participation of foreign enterprises, and promoted the development of the financial market of the ecosystem.

Human Capital

The colleges and educational institutes around the development zone are important places for cultivating outstanding ecosystem talents. Excellent human resources are the key to promoting regional development, which can improve the quality and ability of innovative talents, thereby improving the completion efficiency of the ecosystem.

Bank

Banking institutions can provide long-term and stable financial support for the development of enterprises. Enterprises in the ecosystem need the support of bank funds. The loans and funds of banking institutions can ensure the normal operation of enterprise operations and provide sufficient financial support for entrepreneurial activities.

Figure 2: Chengdu Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Map

Education

Educational institutions and schools cultivate outstanding talents for the development of the ecosystem, and provide human support for enterprises in the ecosystem. The capacity development of schools plays a key role in the activities of the ecosystem.

Medical

Medical service solves the health problems of enterprise personnel, provides health services for personnel, strengthens the service sector in the ecosystem, and promotes the medical knowledge of personnel in the innovation zone and the improvement of service quality of medical institutions.

3 Leverage Proposal

3.1 Our Vision

Why?

In accordance with the original development plans and challenges of EE in the High Tech Zone, our group agreed that the focus of the next ten years of development planning will remain on the sustainability of the three major technology start-up parks: the Bio town, the Business Park, and the Technology Park. In addition, the High Tech Zone EE has spawned a wave of entrepreneurship, with more nascent technology start-ups in the future, but a preponderance of low- quality and stress-resistant start-up industries. Due to social and environmental issues, inadequate resource allocation and capital utilisation, most small and medium-sized technology start-ups will fail (MA, 2022). Further, due to social environment concerns, poor resource allocation, and capital utilisation, most small and medium-sized technological startups discontinue EE development in the Hi-Tech Zone (MA, 2022). This is particularly true for foreign technology startups that lack access to local market participants and customers. The absence of small and medium-sized enterprises in the High Tech Zone EE can result in a fragile economy, and the limited room for development hinders the local government's ability to attract foreign investment. Even though the government has developed a financial assistance programme for small and medium-sized digital startups, there is still a lack of funding (CHENGDU HI - TECH ZONE, 2020) However, the threshold for applying for financial support is insufficiently stringent, resulting in the possibility of receiving financial resources without generating economic returns in a short period of time, or even the failure of research and development leading to the abandonment of the project. Therefore, if small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are to grow gradually over time and make efficient use of local resources, they require strong rules and effective methods. The consistent expansion of SMBs in the High Tech Zone EE will contribute to the future economic stability of the High Tech Zone EE.

What?

Our team has taken a deep insight at what is currently on show at the Chengdu High-Tech Zone EE, and has analysed the current prospects to accommodate more small and medium-sized technology innovation sectors in the future, while moving away from a single technology start-up as the backbone. For example, as a platform with a well-established system of services, the High Tech Zone EE may attract and create additional food start-ups in the local office area to provide for the daily needs of the working class in the EE region. At the same time additional small and medium-sized technological start-ups might create more jobs and the position of attracting talent. In speaking with stakeholders in the High Tech EE System Board, it was noted that they have placed a strong emphasis on the development of small and medium-sized technology start-ups and the creation of jobs to attract talent, as well as encouraging the development of a diversity of start-ups and businesses in the region. This is not only to strengthen the multi-branding and diversity of the Tech park, Biotown and Business City business districts, but also to give a better platform for other start-ups and other sectors to develop and collaborate.

3.2 Lever 1

How & When?

Our team wants to divide this implementation proposal into a 10-year plan, the objective is to enhance the quality of small and medium-sized technology companies in the high-tech zone EE and the regional economic standing. Further, at each stage of the plan, we will push key stakeholders to participate in the programme and urge them to move forward. Throughout the process, stakeholders will be provided with a comprehensive understanding of their function and position within the EE system. The detailed strategy is as follows:

First, the High-Tech Zone Government will improve its policy on economic support for small and medium-sized startups and build an economic support policy hierarchy. Generally, on the basis of the number of small and medium-sized technological startups who seeking for economic assistance, it is anticipated that their current products will be capable of creating economic output within a short period of time. If the existing product can provide short-term economic advantages (Tingting, 2022) and bring financial returns to the stakeholders, it will be eligible for business accessing financial support. The quantity of financial support received is proportional to the future economic advantages created by the product. Improving the policy will ensure that the quality of small and medium-sized technology startups in the High Tech Zone EE

increases substantially (Central and provincial media, 2022), while maximising the use of limited funding resources. In the case that finance is still insufficient, the government might appeal to banks for startup business loans with lower interest rates (MA, 2022).

Second, it is crucial to encourage networking and cooperation among SMEs in order to expand their products' exposure to the community and to promote their products in the market economy. The absence of capital investment and the stagnation of projects that create economic benefits contribute to the short lifespan of the majority of SME enterprises. Consequently, the government guides SME firms to extend the size of the local market economy by offering a publicity platform for their products, sales channels, and possibilities to increase client base. It is required that every quarter, on a public stage, a product promotion fair is hosted for small and medium-sized technology start-ups to showcase their new goods. Especially for foreign tech startups, a strong local customer will ensure they can sell their products in the early stages and earn a stable income to keep the business afloat. (Chengdu Hi-Tech Zone, 2022). In addition, the administration of the Hi-Tech Zone can use quarterly product sales and the financial health of technology enterprises as factors for evaluating their future requests for financial aid. The partition of zones for SMEs, where there would be a variety of start-ups inside a zone, might make a good closed-loop cross-industry collaboration circle, thereby facilitating interactions and cooperation between businesses. For instance, a gaming startup that requires awareness for a new product can work with a nearby media startup. Promoting a strong collaboration is advantageous to the stable development of small and medium-sized enterprises.

Additionally, as a technology startup EE, technological products will attract visitors or technology explorers, therefore an exhibition centre will be constructed in the small area to showcase the works of small and medium-sized technology startups. In addition, food and service startups will be constructed in the vicinity of the exhibition centre to provide more opportunities for tourists and locals to enjoy the products and services.

Who?

As one of the stakeholders and a management planner, the ChengDu HI-TECH ZONE government will be active in assuring the program's execution. It is currently in charge of zoning the start-up region, recruiting start-ups, managing enterprises that switch industries, and updating and executing laws. Based on its function, the Hi-Tech Zone Government can implement strategies and plans for better resource allocation and development policies for small and medium-sized businesses (CHENGDU HI - TECH ZONE, 2020). As the government is responsible for attracting startups, it will be responsible for permitting SMEs to move in, regulating the allocation of resources to startups, and assisting businesses with funding implementation. Historically, the process of financing a business takes between three and five years, and the government assists the startup in obtaining a bank loan (MA, 2022) The loan's interest rate is the corporate standard, which effectively decreases the risk of the company experiencing a short-term cash shortage in the supply chain.

Value

As one of the stakeholders, the ChengDu HI -TECH government is also active in the programme as a planner and leader to ensure that the programme is implemented. The EE region as a whole requires large technological enterprises as economic leaders and SMEs as the region's economic base. SMEs are a diversified and entrepreneurial group that may fill market shortages and produce goods and services in the EE region. (Tingting, 2022) However, the majority are less risk-tolerant and have shorter lifespans. Therefore, policies that prioritise and assist small and medium-sized enterprises can enable them to get a reasonable allocation of resources and a stable environment for growth. While the regional economy will continue to grow steadily, the stability of the development space will aid the government in attracting more high-quality startups and large technology firms to the region. Moreover, the presence of more SMEs will enhance employment in the region, which will improve industrial output, labour income, and government tax revenue. With a continual growth in government tax revenues, SME support policies can be applied more consistently or even expanded. The variety of products and services provided by SME start-ups will attract locals and foreigners to a certain extent. High-tech, new technologies, and entrepreneurial sectors can stimulate the minds of tourists, who will then share their experiences and photographs on social media platforms, thereby boosting the visibility of local firms and innovations.

Adverse effects

The over reliance of businesses on government subsidies, resulting in a squeezing effect, is one of the documented negative outcomes (Jia et al., 2021) Initially, government subsidies diminish the research expenses of businesses. There is a propensity for businesses to over invest in initiatives as a result of the reduced cost pressure. Researchers squander an inordinate amount of funds. Ultimately, this results in squandered R&D funds and decreased production.

3.3 Lever 2: Attracting Talent

How & When?

In the media interviews, we captured some experts' discussions on the talent problem in Chengdu. "Chengdu has better university resources because there are many excellent local universities, such as Sichuan University, University of Electronic Science and Technology of China, and Southwestern University of Finance and Economics," But leaving these schools aside, we can find that talents from Tsinghua University, Peking University and even some foreign universities seldom choose to work in Chengdu. So in terms of talent cost performance, Chengdu High-tech Zone and Chengdu's top talents are still too few."

Zhou said. He also mentioned that the development of CDHT needs diversified talents, not only in technology but also in management, finance, audit, legal affairs, and operation. If Chengdu High-tech Zone wants to develop unicorn entrepreneurial and innovative enterprises, it is not feasible to lack high-end and diversified talents. "Attracting talent is difficult, but retaining talent is even harder," Wang said in an interview. Living is the basic condition, and a job is the key. In terms of living, take the biological town as an example. Regarding policy, talents can prioritise renting and purchasing designated apartments and houses, enjoying medical treatment, and their children can study in designated colleges and universities. Address the concerns of talents in health care and education. In terms of life services, the biological town has built urban parks, commercial complexes and commercial streets supporting the primary school, kindergarten and hospital. The total area of life and commerce is about 1 million square meters, covering the employees and residents of the park, forming a commercial consumption scene of eating, living, travelling, shopping and entertainment. (CHENGDU HI-TECH ZONE, 2022) The construction policy of integrating industry and city and balancing work and living has been implemented. In terms of employment entrepreneurship, in 2015, Chengdu formally issued the "Chengdu business" Tianfu "action plan", which referred to a set of up to 2 billion RMB for talent development funding for top talent and give comprehensive fund of 50 million RMB, Chengdu will establish an outstanding talents system and give bonuses, while strengthening the financial support of innovative undertaking. (APPENDIX) The Government of Chengdu has attached great importance to introducing talents and solving the worries of living and working in peace and contentment for talents. But many students who graduated from China's top universities or returned from overseas study, as Zhou said, do not consider Chengdu as their first choice for business or personal development.

In Chengdu High-tech Zone, in the construction of high-quality development and innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystem, we believe that openness and high-end leadership are very important. We believe CDHT is open to policies formulated by relevant stakeholders and the construction of urban ecology, but the high-tech zone needs new leaders and relevant activities or enterprises to set the cultural benchmarks. Taking note of Kun's article (2011), he says that China's innovative development is a political phenomenon driven by nationalistic entrepreneurship, through which China has successfully attracted many foreign-trained Chinese to return home and develop self-innovation.

Focusing on the local area of Chengdu, we believe that we can make use of localism and the sense of belonging of Sichuan talents to hold activities to publicize the high-tech zone and attract Sichuan talents from all over the country or overseas to return to innovation and entrepreneurship. So we propose to hold the Sichuan people home "activities, mobilize the development of Sichuan entrepreneurs from all over the world to go back to Chengdu in Sichuan province, the three joint CDHT industry-related enterprises and leading enterprises to carry out the local outside talent introduction and recruitment, give play to the role of association of Bridges, to attract professional structure and the related resources provide specialized services for local enterprises. Through TV and network, and recruitment site propaganda expert lectures, strategic discussions of enterprise talents bring topics and impact. Sichuan talents and unicorn enterprises at home and abroad, especially the settlement of unicorn enterprises, can bring traffic and new ideas, new ideas and new business by attracting the business derivative and angel investment of these unicorn enterprises in Chengdu. We also propose to cooperate with overseas offshore talent bases to hold this activity and exert its influence to attract more overseas Sichuan talents. A large number of talents can promote the increase of the number and quality of small and medium-sized start-ups.

Who?

The stakeholders and the drivers of the scheme will also include the government of Chengdu of SICHUAN talent planning appropriate business policy, the policy may include tax breaks for businesses or individuals interest-free or low-interest loans, startup carrier preferential rental price, for the enterprises in the preferential policies of the enterprise, including providing office space location consultation, project cooperation of financial institutions, Application market development. CDHT Technology Talent Bureau organizes recruitment activities and promotes the activities. He Haihua, president of Chengdu Electronic Information Industry Association, chengdu Pharmaceutical and health Industry Ecosystem Alliance, drives

the alliance and internal enterprises of the association to plan human resource strategies and encourages local enterprises to accept Sichuan talents. The proposed leverage will contribute to CDHT's ecosystem development, with the aim of increasing the number and quality of innovative smes and providing more high-end talent to the Chengdu entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Value

Attracting talent through localism, utilising the notion of belonging to a place, is a highly unique concept. Some of these skilled individuals will likely return to their hometowns to work in construction. Utilizing events to promote the theme of hiring Sichuanese talent will be successful in acquiring Sichuanese talent. Simultaneously, the event will be organised overseas to entice Sichuan immigrants to return to the HI - TECH ZONE to construct. This method has the benefit of attracting talent will minimise the cost and expense of recruitment for the government and connected parties as opposed to the use of quality treatment and related policies. Less cost means the government and connected stakeholder companies will have more funds to invest in research projects or to foster entrepreneurial activity among talented individuals. At the same time, the entry of talent increases the total level of labour output in the region (Hu et al., 2020), resulting in more taxes for the local government and larger profits for the enterprises involved, which contributes to an increase in the region's average income level. Second, the majority of talented individuals seek a stable, long-term work environment and a great quality of life. As a result, the regional environment indicator of EE in the high-tech zone will become more crucial to its development as the number of talented individuals increases. The regional environment index corresponds to fundamental factors including education, healthcare, transportation, and public security (Hu et al., 2020). The regional indicator score will be greater the higher the level of the fundamental elements. Higher regional indicators are beneficial in preventing the brain drain of electrical engineering (EE) expertise from high-tech locations and in attracting more talent to the region.

Identify one disadvantage of adopting the local belonging strategy to attract talent. First, relying on the government and relevant stakeholders to arrange events to encourage the attraction of local talent from Sichuan has a lengthy cycle time and may not be beneficial in the short term. Additionally, geographical indicator scores can influence the effectiveness of Sichuan talent recruitment (Hu et al., 2020). According to one study, Chengdu Hi-Tech Zone is situated in a location that ranks low in China in terms of indicator scores, with low levels of basic variables such as education, healthcare, and home ownership, and cannot be compared to other first-tier cities with high indicator scores. Consequently, the return of Sichuan talent to the Chengdu region will be determined by the EE index ratings for the Chengdu Hi-tech Zone. In addition, for the regional indicator scores to improve in a short period of time, the government and corporate entities with connected interests would need to invest a substantial amount of money.

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